

Nitrous Oxide (N2O) for the Management of Labor

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BACKGROUND

- N2O for labor analgesia was first introduced in England in 1934 and since is estimated that up to 75% of parturient's in Europe, Canada, and Australia use N2O during labor
- In recent years, N2O has been gaining popularity in the US and is now offered in over 500 hospitals and birth care centers across the US
- At high concentrations 65-70% N2O works as a weak anesthetic and produces loss of consciousness
- At subanesthetic concentrations $\leq$ 50% N2O works as an analgesic and anxiolytic
- Labor Experience is Influenced by pain, anxiety, and autonomy
- Labor epidurals, while considered the gold standard for the treatment of labor pain, may be contraindicated in some parturients (or refused)
- N2O can be used as an alternative intervention to alleviate anxiety, decrease pain perception, and improve satisfaction for laboring women

PURPOSE

To create reference material on N2O for labor-management to facilitate the implementation of this intervention at Kaiser Permanente of Southern California (KP SCAL)

Aims:

- To develop a Southern California Permanente Medical Group (SCPMG) Regionally Approved Clinical Reference on N2O
- To gain approval to publish this clinical reference on KP SCAL Clinical Library website

LITERATURE REVIEW

Pain Management and Efficacy of N2O utilization

- 2 Systematic Reviews
 - 21 Studies (Likis et al. 2014)
 - 14 Studies (Sheyklo et al. 2017)
- 6 Individual Studies
 - Observational (1)
 - QI Projects (2)
 - RCT (3)

Measures: VAS & NRS

Patient Satisfaction with of N2O utilization

- 2 Systematic Reviews
 - 9 Studies (Likis et al. 2014)
 - 4 Studies (Sheyklo et al., 2017)
- 5 Individual Studies
 - Observational
 - QI Project
 - RCT
 - Descriptive quantitative (prospective)
 - Qualitative (retrospective)

Measures: Descriptive questionnaires, Satisfaction rating scores, rating likelihood to use N2O again

Screening and Contraindications to Utilization

- Methods in Evaluating risk versus benefits in parturients

Occupational Exposure and Safety

- Potential neurotoxicity with prolonged and high doses (studies on non-human subjects)
- Studies did not show effect on FHR, breastfeeding, APGAR, or behavioral assessment scores
- Limited evidence regarding updated and recent occupational exposure studies

Facilitators and Barriers to Utilization

- 5 QI studies
 - Common barriers identified
 - lack of staff compliance
 - poor staff education

Literature Review Conclusion

Based on evidence N2O is not proven to be effective in every case of labor pain management

N2O demonstrated more effective in parturients desiring:

- Natural birthing experience
- Avoidance of invasive methods
- Maintenance degree of mobility and autonomy

Therefore N2O can be recognized as a:

- Substitute to utilizing narcotics
- Adjunct to nonpharmacologic methods of labor pain management
- Assistant with transition to neuraxial anesthesia

METHODS

Initial Approval

- Identify SCPMG Chiefs of Service or Regional Committees of designated specialty
- Dr. Yen → primary contact for oversight in order to initiate next steps & allow publication on Clinical Library

Development of Clinical Reference

- Perform Literature review
- Develop according to KP SCAL clinical reference policy and formatting
- Approval of clinical reference content by Dr. Yen

Submission and Review of Clinical Reference

- Quality & content review by:
 - SCPMG Assistant Medical Directors
 - KP SCAL Quality & Risk Management
 - KP SCAL Reference/Guideline Management Team

Final Approval and Updates

- Quality and Clinical Analysis required prior to publication by SCPMG Assistant Medical Director
- Update required every two years

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The Iow Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

LIMITATIONS

Obstetrical Anesthesia Changes During COVID-19

- Current literature does not recommend the utilization of N2O administration in the setting of COVID 19
- Resources and financial dollars diverted towards management of Covid-19 pandemic
- More concrete evidence needed regarding:
 - Safe administration practices
 - Proper device cleaning and filtering
 - Potential for aerosolization associated with N2O utilization

FACILITATORS

- Team Lead: Jen Thompson
- Clinical site:
 - Kaiser Permanente Fontana Medical Center
- SCPMG Physician Sponsor: Dr. Yen

OUTCOME

- Clinical Reference guideline for the use of N2O for the management of labor
- Approved and evaluated by Dr. Yen, a board certified KP Anesthesiologist who specializes in obstetrical anesthesia
- To be submitted for publication in the future following subsiding of the COVID-19 pandemic